

Research

Safety Study of Road Freight Transportation along the One Belt One Road Countries Based on Vehicle Dynamics

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Accepted: 10 Aug, 2020; Online: 25 Aug, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4001197>

Abstract: "Belt and Road Initiative" (BRI) proposed by China regarding the concept of "connectivity" and the significance of "sharing the future community" in the new era focuses on the international road freight transport. During the time of highway transportation, once there is a traffic accident, it will truly influence the productivity and effectiveness of merchandise flow. The bond between the vehicle parameters of the heavy semi-trailer and the road parameters of the mountain road is an essential parameter to study before the constructions of road. The purpose of this research is to develop the safe and accident-free roadways which ultimately will promote the uniform traffic rules and make the unified regulations on load. In order to deeply study the stability of semitrailer in the process of driving on a mountain highway, the software named TruckSim is used as analyzing tool that establishes the whole vehicle simulation driving system composed of semi-trailer model, road model and driver model.

This paper studies the factors such as speed, specific power of a vehicle, load capacity, gradient of longitudinal slope, radius of curve, corner of curve, transverse gradient of curve, position of load center of mass, etc., which affect the running speed, lateral acceleration, longitudinal acceleration and shift times of driver of a semi-trailer. When driving uphill, the average longitudinal acceleration has a linear negative correlation with the initial speed of uphill. Therefore, speed limit and load limit signs can be set in the typical longitudinal slope section of the mountain highway to remind drivers to pay attention. This research also provides calculating parameters and a control basis for operating speed prediction, load and limit value determination for the road slope gradient and radius of curve.

The road model is established with the longitudinal gradient of 3%, 4%, 5% and 6%. At the same time, the load of the whole vehicle is changed, and then the uphill simulation is carried out at different initial speeds. When the vehicle load is 30t and the initial speed is 70-80 km/h, the speed difference of the vehicle is small, the semi-trailer train is safer in the uphill driving process. With the increase of the specific power of the semitrailer train, the minimum running speed of the vehicle in the process of climbing increases. For every 0.01kw/kg increase of the specific power, the increment of the minimum running speed V_{min} of the semi-trailer train is close to 10 km/h.

When the semitrailer train passes the curve at a speed of 70 km/h ~ 90 km/h, the lateral force is enough to ensure the normal driving of the vehicle, the lower the longitudinal

gradient, the more obvious the influence of the speed of the vehicle on the lateral curve acceleration. When the curve radius is not less than 350m, and the curve angle is greater than 7.5° and rises slowly, the vehicle's lateral acceleration adjustment in the curve is very minimal. The value of lateral acceleration increases slowly with the increasing speed of a vehicle. To make sure that the vehicle can pass the curve at a higher speed without sideslip or even rollover, the method of increasing the cross slope of the curve can be adopted. When the vehicle is travelling at a speed of 80 km/h on the downhill, the distance between load centroid and the front axle D_1 should be less than or equal to 7000 mm and the distance between load centroid and ground D_2 should be less than or equal to 2300 mm, so that the semitrailer can maintain a stable driving state. It is hoped that the countries along the BRI will get a reference for the road safety standards

Keywords: Road freight Transportation, Belt and Road Initiative, Vehicle dynamics, Trucksim

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and Significance of the Research

In the 3.0 period of economic globalization, emerging economies represented by China have risen and are merging into the evolution and choice of the new order of economic globalization with a strong momentum, forming a new geographic pattern that weakens hegemony, is more inclusive and balanced [1]. China hosted the second "Belt and Road Initiative" summit in Beijing on 25-27 April 2019. The national strategy for "Belt and Road Initiative" is international road freight transport. China government has signed cooperation document in the field of transportation with the government of Pakistan, Liberia, Nepal, Laos, Mongolia, Kazakhstan and Russia [2]. There are widespread traffic inconveniences and relatively backward infrastructure. To promote economic development and realize the design importance of "Belt and Road Initiative", the safety of highway transportation must be taken seriously. The safety of highway transport must be taken seriously in order to promote economic development and realize the design importance of the "Belt and Road Initiative". In 2015, only 33% of the total cargo transported by China and foreign countries was transported. Especially the non-uniformity of vehicle size, axle load and maximum allowable permissible gross mass limit of the vehicles, dimensions and quality standards between China and countries outside it, entering a vehicle that engaged in international road freight transport from their neighboring countries to China is very difficult [3]. So it is urgent to determine the relevant standards of technical requirements for the selection of international road cargo transport vehicles, which will help road transport enterprises to go out to participate in international competition and realize the fairness and vigorous

development of international road freight transport. For the effective and implementable traffic management, China has to adopt such a legislation to safeguard, promote, guide and regulate to those road traffic management organizations and related institutions with international cooperation and giving the conducive environment for better co-ordination within and outside the country [4]. Currently China-Pakistan Economic Corridor; Bangladesh-China-India-Myanmar Economic Corridor; China-Mongolia-Russia Economic Corridor; China-Indo-China Peninsula [5] are the main land route corridors along the "Belt and Road Initiative". Countries along the line have introduced different standards for transport vehicles [6] and in order to increase the carrying capacity, transport companies usually use semitrailer as the main means of transport. These vehicles have a large mass and volume. Therefore, in order to ensure the road transport safety, the relationship between the vehicle parameters such as load mass, average speed, specific power, longitudinal acceleration, an initial speed of uphill and the road parameters such as slope value and steering angle is required to be studied.

1.2 Problems in Road Transportation about the safety along with the belt and road

The roads along the "one belt one road" are mostly built in the middle of the mountain due to the topography and climate in the western part of China, and the roadbed conditions are relatively bad. Total length of the highway along the 'Belt and Road Initiative' is long and it faces enormous coordination problems in road maintenance and inspection across many countries and regions, and cannot guarantee real-time road safety. The vehicle's endurance needs timely water, oil, maintenance and other supplies. Once the supplies are not in all place, the vehicle is prone to problems during transportation. Based on the statistics of the transport vehicles along the highway along the route, we can find that most of the vehicles along the road are mainly heavy trucks. Such vehicles are difficult to operate when they encounter some slope road conditions, and often occur rollover, side slip, rear-end collision and other accidents. Infrastructure construction plans in different countries are inconsistent.

The national conditions of each country are different, so the legal and technical standards vary greatly. The number of transport routes between Guangxi and Vietnam is increasing, but there are still some problems in cross-border transport, such as laws, regulations, systems and technology [7]. Information is not exchanged among the

participating departments of various countries. The coordination mechanism between China and other countries and domestic departments is not smooth. Due to the different degree of development of each country, the consideration of interests in the process of cooperation is also different.

1.3 Significance of the Research

Practical Significance

The research was carried out to tackle the practical aspect of the vehicle dynamics with the road freight transportation along with one belt one road. The major practical hurdles are listed below:

1. What are the problems faced by road transportation safety along with the "one belt and one road" countries?
2. How to promote economic development and realize the design importance of "Belt and Road Initiative", through road transportation?
3. What are the parameters of vehicle safety measure to ensure highway safety along with one belt one road countries?
4. What is the correlation between average longitudinal acceleration and with the initial speed of the semi-trailer while driving in uphill
5. What is to be addressed with the speed limit and weight limit in typical longitudinal grade zones of the Mountainous highway?
6. How to determine the relationship between torque and inclination angle?
7. How is the variation of K in slope value does takes place with the topographic condition?
8. How to check the validation of theoretical aspects for optimization in practically?

The real significance of the study is to ensure the safety of a heavy semi-trailer vehicles along the highway by studying the relationship between vehicle parameters and road parameters, so that the relevant countries can get out the corresponding road traffic rules along the mountain roads along the Belt and Road Initiative to reduce the occurrence of traffic accidents.

1.4 Purpose of the Research

Focusing at the characteristics of the highway along with the "Belt and Road Initiative" located in the mountainous area, this paper considers the driving characteristics of a semi-trailer train on the longitudinal road section of the road.

This paper analyzes the objective rules of the influence of each factor on the running stability of the semitrailer train from the following factors: the running speed of the semitrailer train, the load capacity of the semitrailer train, the longitudinal gradient value of the road, the corner of the curve, the radius of the curve, the position of the centroid of the vehicle load and so on. This paper studies the dynamic performance and speed characteristics of semitrailer train running on the uphill section of mountain highway, as well as the stability of vehicle running on the downhill curve of highway, which provides the basis for the designer to set the geometric parameters such as the horizontal curve radius, longitudinal slope of the road.

1.5 Main Content of the Research

The simulation running system of semitrailer train is established. The vehicle model, road model and driver model are established by using TruckSim simulation software. For the vehicle model, the tractor and semi-trailer models need to be established respectively, and the corresponding characterization parameters are set.

The 3D surface module is used to build roads with different longitudinal slope, turning radius and turning angle, and to set the road material, friction coefficient and cross slope.

This paper studies and analyzes the influence of different initial running speed, different longitudinal gradient and vehicle load on the climbing speed characteristics of six axle heavy semitrailer train. The initial driving speed changes are 50 km/h, 60 km/h, 70 km/h and 80 km/h, the longitudinal slope changes are 3%, 4%, 5% and 6%, and the vehicle load change range is 20t ~ 50t.

Using the method of real vehicle test and simulation, this paper studies the stability of semi-trailer train running on the downhill curve of mountain highway, determination the geometric parameters such as downhill curve radius, curve turning (left and right turning), curve turning angle, longitudinal slope and transverse slope of the road, and

analyzes the change of semi-trailer train running state on the curve. The influence of the position of the vehicle's load center of mass on the vehicle's turning stability is also addressed.

Fig. 1. Technical Route of Research

2. The Status of Highway Transportation along the “Belt and Road Initiative”

China has signed 44 bilateral and multilateral automobile transport regulations with neighboring countries, which laid the foundation for the development of international road transport. There are cooperation mechanisms related to road transport facilitation in China. According to the national standard GB1589-2016, at present, freight vehicles in China are mainly divided into trucks, semi-trailers, semi-trailers, full trailers and mid-axle trailer. In the process of formulating standards, the following principles are followed: first, to meet the relevant requirements of national laws and regulations such as the People's Republic of China's Road Traffic Regulation. Second, compliance with bilateral or multilateral transport agreements and their arrangements. The third is to meet the requirements of GB 1589 and GB 7258, and the fourth is to embody the principles of fairness and coordination [8]. The length limit of trucks in all countries should be 12m. The max length of articulated vehicle is 17.1m, Width should not exceeding 2.5m and Height should not exceed 4.2m. The maximum allowable total mass limits of truck for 6 axles is 49000 kg.

3. Establishment of vehicle model simulation system

3.1 Dynamic Analyses of Vehicles

Forces and moments from the road act on every vehicle's tire and greatly influence the vehicle's dynamics. Vehicle speed has a major effect on road accidents, and more severe road accidents are curved sections of road. As vehicle load quality increases, the vehicle's safe speed at the curve section decreases. When the height of the center of gravity of the cargo increases, the vehicle's safe speed in the curve section decreases, the vehicle safety velocity threshold and center height relationship model is linear function of the driving speed, driving speed difference and vehicle lateral acceleration are important factors that affect traffic safety [9].

3.2 The Introduction of TruckSim

TruckSim is a powerful reenactment programming for cargo vehicles and transports created by MSC (Mechanical Simulink Corporation) of the United States [10].

Fig. 2. Trucksim Simulation Experiment System

3.3. The Entire Vehicle Model

The structure of a heavy semi-trailer is complex. We divide this type of vehicle into four main parts, and models are established respectively. Combined with the whole vehicle model, it mainly includes nine aspects: Tractor model, Semitrailer train model, Trailer load, Aerodynamics model, Steering system model, Tire model, Suspension system model, Power transmission system model, Brake system model. For these nine parts, the basic structural parameters of each part are established separately, and the values are set.

The power of the whole vehicle model is all output by the 300 kW tractor engine, and the tractor model is mainly composed of five parts: body, steering system, braking system, power transmission system and driving system.

Fig.3. Coordinate system of the tractor

Fig.4. Appearance model of tractor

Table 1 Basic structural parameters of 3A Cab Over

Parameters	Value
Sprung Mass of Tractor(kg)	8200
Width(mm)	2438
Height(mm)	3200
Distance between vehicle centroid and front axle(mm)	2000
Distance between vehicle centroid and vehicle longitudinal symmetry plane(mm)	0
Distance between vehicle centroid and ground(mm)	1175
Roll Inertia(kg·m ²)	2283.9
Pitch Inertia(kg·m ²)	35402.8
Yaw Inertia(kg·m ²)	34802.6

Productx-y(kg·m ²)	0
Productx-z(kg·m ²)	1626
Producty-z(kg·m ²)	0
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Parameters	Valu
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Sprung Mass of semi-trailer(kg)	6520
Length(mm)	1239
Width(mm)	2480
Height(mm)	2700
Distance between vehicle centroid and front axle(mm)	3400
Distance between vehicle centroid and vehicle longitudinal symmetry plane(mm)	0
Distance between vehicle centroid and ground(mm)	1936
Roll Inertia(kg·m ²)	8997
Pitch Inertia(kg·m ²)	1500
	00
Yaw Inertia(kg·m ²)	1500
	00
Productx-y(kg·m ²)	0
Productx-z(kg·m ²)	0
Producty-z(kg·m ²)	0
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3.4 Road Model

3D surface (all properties) module of the vehicle system is get through TruckSim .The whole vehicle road driving simulation system includes three parts: road model, vehicle model and driver model.

Fig. 5. Appearance of a slope road model

Fig. 6. Side view of a slope road model

This is a two lane model, which simulates a one-way driving environment. Design speed is maintain around 80km/h ~ 120km/h, including two lanes. Each lane is 3.75m wide (highway design standard), and the overall length of the road model is 5km.

4. Research on characteristics of Heavy Semi-trailer When Go up the Slope Road

Using TruckSim software to establish the whole vehicle driving simulation system model, and further studies and analyzes the influence of different initial driving speed, different longitudinal gradient and vehicle load (or total vehicle mass) on the climbing of heavy-duty semitrailer train, as well as the interaction between the three.

The slope value of highway is in the range of 2% ~ 5%, considering the geographical conditions of mountainous areas. Therefore, when building the road model of mountainous areas, the slope value is 3%, 4%, 5%, 6%.

The paper sets the running speed of six-axis heavy semi-trailer reaching the bottom of the slope as 50 km/h, 60 km/h, 70 km/h and 80 km/h for to studying vehicle safety as it goes up the slope road.

Table 2 Values of initial speed, gradient and load capacity in the simulation system

V (km/h)	i (%)	M (t)
50	3	20,30,40,45,50
	4	30,35,40,45,50
	5	21,30,36,40,45,50
	6	15,20,30,35
60	3	30,40,45,50
	4	20,30,35,40,45,50
	5	20,30,36,40,45,50
	6	10,15,21,30,35
70	3	21,30,40,50
	4	20,30,35,36,40,35,50
	5	20,30,36,40,45,50
	6	19,20,21,30,35,40,,45,50
80	3	21,30,40,50
	4	20,30,35,36,40,45,50
	5	20,30,35,36,40,45,50
	6	10,15,20,21,30,35

In the table, the V represents the initial speed of the vehicle when going up the slope, i is the gradient value of the ramp's longitudinal slope, and M is the weight of the semitrailer. Take the longitudinal gradient value of 3% as an example. When a load of semi-trailer and the value of longitudinal gradient are constant, the six axle heavy semi-trailer drives over the slope road section at different initial speeds.

If the longitudinal slope is small and the load of the vehicle is light, the speed of the vehicle will not be reduced with initial speeds of 50 km / h, 60 km / h, 70 km / h and 80 km / h (as shown in the blue lines A and B in Figure. When the vehicle will go uphill with higher load capacity at different initial speeds, during the uphill process, the vehicle speed will gradually reduce to the

lowest speed for uphill driving. After that, the driver will change gears, the vehicle speed will pick up to a certain extent and then drive on the uphill at a stable speed.

Fig. 7. Change of vehicle speed with formal distance during climbing

With the increase in initial driving speed, the longer the vehicle approaches the minimum driving speed, and in the process of uphill driving, the higher the vehicle speed and load, the more often the driver shifts (as shown in (C) and (D) in Figure, that is, the driver load increases.

Fig. 8. Change of vehicle speed with formal distance during climbing

4.1 Minimum Running Speed and Average Longitudinal Acceleration of Semi-Trailer When It Is Going Up Slope

Fig. 9. Minimum driving speed during vehicle climbing

It can be seen that when the semi-trailer load capacity is more than 30t (excluding 30t), and the semi-trailer is driven at the initial speed of 50km / ~ 80km / h, the driving speed of the vehicle will gradually decrease when it passes the slope with the gradient value of 3% ~ 6%.

Analysis shows that the minimum running speed of the six axle truck on the ramp is negatively related to the vehicle load m in the process of climbing.

When the vehicle load is constant, with the gradual increase of the gradient value, the minimum running speed of the vehicle shows a downward trend, and the influence of the change of the vehicle load on the minimum running speed of the vehicle becomes obvious.

Fig. 10. Average longitudinal acceleration during vehicle climbing

It shows that under different “slope-load” simulation conditions, the average longitudinal acceleration a of the vehicle has a significant linear negative correlation with the initial climbing speed V

$$a = -kV + b$$

The absolute value of the average longitudinal acceleration a of the vehicle increases with the increase of the slope value and with the increase of the vehicle load. From the overall analysis, the average longitudinal acceleration a of the vehicle varies from -0.05m/s^2 to -0.3m/s^2 with the initial speed V of the slope when the vehicle is running on the slope with the slope value of 3% - 6% from the overall study.

4.2 Stable Climbing Distance

When semi-trailer loads goods and drives from the bottom of the slope to the top of the slope, the speed decreases gradually. The distance S that the semi-trailer train drives from the initial speed V to the minimum running speed V_{\min} on the slope is called the stable climbing distance. As shown in Figure the stable climbing distance S changes with the initial speed, load capacity and longitudinal gradient of the road.

Fig. 11. Influence of Initial Speed of Vehicle on Stable climbing distance

When the slope value is 3% and the vehicle speed is 60 km/h, the stable climbing distance increases with the increase of vehicle load, as shown in the red line in the Figure. It can be seen from the analysis that when the gradient value $i \leq 4\%$ and the vehicle speed $V \leq 60\text{km/h}$, the load capacity

will increase, and the stable climbing distance S will also increase accordingly. When the vehicle speed $60 \text{ km/h} < V \leq 70 \text{ km/h}$, the change of load capacity will have no obvious effect on the stable climbing distance, as seen in the figure in the blue line. If the speed $V \geq 80 \text{ km/h}$, the increase of semi-trailer weight will cause the stable climbing distance. The distance decreases gradually, as shown in the purple line.

4.2 The Final Uniform Speed of the Vehicle During Going Up Slope

Fig. 12. Final Speed of Vehicle

The comprehensive comparative analysis of figure (A) (B) (C) (D) shows that the speed V' decreases with the increase of vehicle load m , the speed V' has a negative correlation with the gradient i , and with the gradual increase of the longitudinal gradient of the road, the load shift will have a more evident effect on the constant speed V of the vehicle. In (A), the slope value is 3%, and the range of V' value changes with the change of load capacity is 40 km/h~70 km/h. In(C), the slope value is 5%, and the range of V' value is 20 km/h~60 km/h. The length of the range increases.

When the vehicle load is 20t and 30t, i.e. $M \leq 30t$, driving on the ramp with the initial speed value of 50km/h and the gradient value i of 3%, the driver should change the gear once to ensure that the vehicle is able to ride the ramp at a steady speed of 50 km/h. The vehicle can pass the ramp with gradient $i \leq 4\%$ at the speed of 50km/h when $M \leq 20t$. When the gradient value $i > 4\%$, with the

increase of vehicle load M , the speed V' passing through the ramp will drop sharply, that is, when $M > 35t$, driving over the ramp with the gradient value of 4% ~ 6% at the initial speed of 50km/h ~ 80km/h, the speed will drop significantly, and the speed difference $V - V'$ relatively large, which is easy to cause vehicle rear-end accidents.

4.4 Analysis of the Influence of Vehicle specific power

Fig. 13. Influence of specific power of semitrailer on vehicle climbing speed

The results in the figure show that for every 0.01kW/kg increase of the specific power, the increment of the minimum running speed V_{min} of the semi-trailer train is close to 10km/h. In order to maintain the best driving condition, the driver's gear shifting measures, in the process of vehicle climbing, with the increase of specific power of the vehicle, the vehicle dynamics is good, the number of gear shifting is reduced, and the driver's workload is correspondingly reduced.

4.5 Analysis of the Influence of Road Longitudinal Slope

Changing the ramp's longitudinal gradient would impact not only the minimum running speed, the vehicle's uniform running speed and the average longitudinal acceleration, but also affect the driver of the six axle heavy semi-trailer train in the process of climbing and the vehicle following the vehicle.

The longitudinal gradient of the ramp can seriously affect the vehicle's speed during the driving phase, and the quality of the goods loaded by the vehicle will also seriously affect the speed of the vehicle on the slope. Moreover, due to the relationship of inertia, the larger a load of the heavy truck is, the stronger the inertia force is, and the inertia force will also affect the speed change during the uphill driving.

4.6 Influence of Load on Stable Climbing Distance

Fig. 14. Stable climbing distance of semitrailer train during uphill driving

Figure (A) shows that when the semi-trailer's initial velocity is 50 km/h, the vehicle's stable climbing distance decreases as the load capacity decreases. Figure (B) shows that the load efficiency increases slowly from 15 t to 35 t when the initial climb speed is 60 km / h, and the climbing distance has a positive correlation with the load capacity. When the load capacity exceeds 35 t, the climbing distance decreases gradually with the increase of the load capacity. Figure (C) (D) shows the results: when the initial speed of the vehicle climbing is not less than 70kmh, the stable climbing distance decreases with the increase of the load during the vehicle climbing.

The climbing distance of the semitrailer train has a negative correlation with the road longitudinal gradient, and the negative correlation is more obvious when the speed is higher than 60km/h. Comprehensive analysis shows that when the load capacity of semi-trailer train is less than or equal to 35t, semi-trailer train is safer in the uphill driving process.

5. Study on the Driving Stability of Semi-trailer in Downhill Turning

When the vehicle is loaded with goods and driving uphill, the vehicle speed is 70 km/h ~ 80 km/h, and the speed is gradually lowered to 25 km/h ~ 50 km/h. When the semitrailer train passes the curve at a lower speed, the lateral force is enough to ensure the normal driving of the vehicle.

The overall mass limit for heavy-duty vehicles is 49 T while driving on the expressway, according to the regulations for the implementation of China's road traffic safety legislation when establishing the road driving simulation system of downhill vehicle, the load capacity of semitrailer train is 35t, and the vehicle weight is 49.72t.

5.1 Modeling of Downhill Driving Simulation System

Fig. 15. Vehicle driving status on the downhill road

Table 3 Change of lateral acceleration of curve with angle of curve

i (%)	R (m)	Angle of Bend (°)	V
-3	350	20	70
-3	350	30	70
-3	350	40	70
-3	350	50	70
-3	350	60	70
-3	350	70	70
-3	350	80	70
-3	350	90	70
-3	400	20	70
-3	400	30	70
-3	400	40	70
-3	400	50	70
-3	400	60	70
-3	400	70	70
-3	400	80	70

5.2 Influence of angle of Curve

During driving on the downhill curve the maximum value of the absolute value of the semitrailer train's lateral acceleration is recorded as the "lateral curve acceleration."

The data given are the data with a slope value of -3% and a curve radius of 350m and 400m respectively. The change in curve angle at this time does not affect the maximum value of the vehicle's lateral acceleration running at the curve, according to the simulation results.

Fig. 16. Relationship between lateral acceleration of curve and radius

The longitudinal gradient value of downhill road is divided into -4% and -5%. When the vehicle is driving on the curve, the lateral acceleration of the semi-trailer train changes with the change of the curve radius.

When the radius of the curve is not more than 250m, changing the curve angle would have a certain effect on the vehicle's lateral acceleration in the curve, but the impact is minor. When the curve radius is not less than 300m, the change of the curve angle from 20° to 90° will not cause the change of the lateral acceleration of the vehicle curve.

Fig. 17. Relationship between lateral acceleration of curve and time

With a longitudinal gradient of -6% and a curve radius of 400m at a speed of 70km/h. The wider the curve angle, the longer the time it takes for the vehicle to cross the curve, but the lateral acceleration of the vehicle driving on the curve would not be affected.

Table 4 Change of lateral acceleration of curve with angle, radius and gradient of curve

I (%)	R (m)	Angle of Bend (°)	V (km/h)	A _x
-3	400	5	70	0.109448
		7.5		0.114288
		10		0.114288
		15		0.114288
-4	300	5	70	0.152292
		7.5		0.184866
		10		0.193317
		15		0.193317
-5	500	5	70	0.135764
		7.5		0.140341
		10		0.140341
		15		0.140341
-6	350	5	70	0.184576
		7.5		0.228011
		10		0.236666
		15		0.236665

When curve angle greater than 20°, the vehicle's lateral acceleration won't increase with the corner of the curve, and a change in the curve corner does not impact the vehicle's lateral acceleration when it is driving at the slope corner.

The influence of the corner angle on the lateral acceleration of the six axle heavy semi-trailer is studied when the corner angle changes in the range of 5° ~ 15°.

When the curve radius is not greater than 300 m, the six axle heavy semi-trailer will drive on the downhill curve, the curve angle of the road will gradually increase from 0° to 7.5°, and with the rise of the curve angle, the vehicle's lateral acceleration in the Y-axis direction will slowly increase. When the radius of the curve is not less than 350m, the angle of the curve gradually increases from 7.5° to 90°. The change of the angle of the curve has no effect on the maximum value of the absolute acceleration in the Y-direction.

5.3 Effect of Driving Speed

Fig. 18. Effect of vehicle speed on lateral acceleration

The centripetal acceleration of the six axle heavy semi-trailer is $A_y = V^2/r$ when it makes circular motion on the curve. It can be seen that the speed and radius of the six axle load vehicle will affect the vehicle's lateral acceleration during the downhill curve driving process

When driving at the speed of 70 km/h, 80 km/h and 90 km/h when the corner of the curve is 20°, 60° and 90, the value of lateral acceleration in Y-axis direction increases slowly with the increase speed of vehicle, that is, the greater the speed is, the more obvious the trend of vehicle side slip is shown.

Fig.19. Effect of vehicle speed on lateral acceleration of vehicle turning downhill

Corner of the curve is 20°. Results as shown in figure (A) (B) (C) (D) are obtained, which respectively reflect the relationship between the lateral acceleration and speed of the six axle heavy semi-trailer with slope values of -3%, -4%, -5%, -6%. Compared with the four figures, it can be seen that the speed changes in the range of 70km/h ~ 80km/h, and the maximum absolute value of the lateral acceleration changes in the range of 0.1m/s² ~ 0.4m/s² during the of the vehicle’s downhill curve driving process. The value of lateral acceleration will increase with the increase of vehicle speed. The relationship between vehicle speed and lateral acceleration is positive. The change of acceleration in Y direction will decrease with the increase of curve radius. This result can be seen from the distance between blue line, red line and purple line.

The value of lateral acceleration will gradually decrease with the increase of the radius of the road curve as the vehicle travels from the straight downhill section to the downhill curve section.

5.4 Analysis on the Influence of Cross Slope of Curve

When the vehicle turns in the curve without the cross slope of the road, the centripetal acceleration formula of the vehicle is:

$$A_Y = \frac{v^2}{r}$$

When the vehicle has a curve cross slope, the calculation formula of the cross slope value is:

$$i_h = \frac{v^2}{127r} \pm \mu$$

Table 5 Change of driving state of six-axle truck with vehicle speed

Number	R	hi	V	States
1			80	Normal
2		0	90	Side slip
3			110	Rollover
4			90	Normal
5	300	6	100	Side slip
6			120	Rollover
7			100	Normal
8		10	110	Side slip
9			125	Rollover
10			120	Normal
11	600	10	130	Side slip
12			145	Rollover

When driving on a road with a cross slope of 0% and a speed of 90km/h, the six axle vehicle will slip. When the radius of 300m curve is 10% and the speed reaches 110km/h, the six axle vehicle will slip. When the expressway is built in mountainous area, due to the limitation of geographical location, it cannot be guaranteed that the road has a large turning radius. In order to make sure that the vehicle can pass the curve at a higher speed without side slip or even rollover, the method of increasing the cross slope of the curve can be adopted. When a six axle loaded vehicle passes a downhill curve with a radius of 300m, the vehicle can still maintain a normal speed of 100km/h when the cross slope value of the curve is 10%.

5.5 Analysis of the Influence of Load Centroid Position on Vehicle Driving Stability

The distance between load centroid and the front axle is recorded as D_1 , and the distance between load centroid and ground is recorded as D_2 .

The larger the D_1 is, the more serious the semi-trailer's tail flick and side slip are. Figure indicates a transition in the lateral instantaneous acceleration of the vehicle with time when the distance between the middle of the load and the front axle is 6000 mm, 7000 mm, 8000 mm, 9000 mm, and the downhill curve of the semitrailer train as shown in Figure(A), (B), (C) and (D). The cumulative time of the route driving simulation method is set as 100s during the simulation.

Fig. 20. Effect of D_1 change on vehicle lateral acceleration

When the value of D_1 is less than or equal to 7000mm and the distance between the centroid of load and the front axle changes, the lateral acceleration of the whole vehicle will not be affected. When the value of D_1 is 8000 mm, the semi-trailer train running on the curve is very unstable and serious side slip occurs. When the value of D_1 is 9000 mm, the vehicle is driving on the downhill curve, and the simulation process ends at 30s, indicating that the vehicle has rollover during driving. Therefore, it can be determined that when the value of D_1 is less than or equal to 7000 mm, the vehicle can safely drive through the curve.

When the distance D_2 from the center of load to the ground is 2300 mm, 3300 mm, 4300 mm and 4800 mm, the shift in the lateral acceleration of the vehicle with the time the semitrailer train runs on the downhill curve is as follows.(A), (B), (C) and (D). The total simulation time is 100s.

Fig. 21. Effect of D_2 change on vehicle lateral acceleration

When the value of D_2 is less than or equal to 2300mm, the semitrailer train keeps stable running on the curve with a longitudinal gradient of -3% on the downhill. When the distance between the centroid of load and the ground is 3300 mm, the vehicle side slip occurs during driving, but the side slip is not obvious. As seen, the orange line in Figure (b). When the value of D_2 is 4300 mm, there is obvious sideslip when the vehicle is driving on the curve, and the red line in Fig. (c) Has obvious fluctuation in 20s ~ 30s. When the value of D_2 is 4800 mm and the semitrailer is driven to 25s, the vehicle will roll over and the simulation will be terminated.

When the load mass of the semitrailer is 35 t, when the vehicle is traveling at a speed of 80 km/h on the downhill curve of the mountain highway, when the value of D_1 is less than or equal to 7000mm and the value of D_2 is less than or equal to 2300mm, the vehicle can maintain a stable driving state.

6. Conclusion and Prospect

In view of the characteristics of highways along the mountain area along the route, the six-axle heavy semi-trailer is chosen as the research vehicle. The running state and safe driving of semi-trailer train on the uphill road and downhill bend road in mountainous area are analyzed. The conclusion is as follows:

- The relationship between the average longitudinal acceleration and the initial uphill speed is linear and negative during uphill driving, i.e. when the slope value is between 3 % and 5 %, the value of K is within the range of (-0.001, -0.002). The value of K is within the range of (-0.0025, -0.0035) (when the slope value is greater than or equal to 6 %). When the vehicle load is 30t and the initial speed is 70-80km / s, the speed difference of the vehicle is small. As a result, speed limit and load limit signs can be set up in typical longitudinal slope sections of Mountainous highway to remind drivers.
- When the gradient value is less than or equal to 4% and the initial speed of vehicle climbing V is not more than 60 km/h, the distance traveled in the process of the speed is affected by the load. Due to the effect of inertial force, the stable climbing distance increases with the increase of vehicle load. If the speed is above 80 km/h, the weight of the semi-trailer increases and the stable climbing distance slowly decreases.

- For every 0.01 kw/kg increase of specific power of the vehicle, the increment of minimum driving speed during uphill driving is nearly 10 km/h. increasing the specific power of the semitrailer train can therefore effectively increase the vehicle's operating speed during the uphill driving cycle process.
- In the process of uphill driving, when the load and gradient are fixed, when the gradient value is less than 3% and the vehicle's load capacity changes within the range of 10t ~ 40t, the increment of the driver's shift times and the increment of the initial driving speed show a linear positive correlation.
- When the speed of the vehicle is 70 km / h ~ 90 km / h, the lower the longitudinal gradient, the more obvious the influence of the speed of the vehicle on the lateral curve acceleration. If the gradient is -3 percent, the change value of the vehicle's lateral acceleration curve is 0.2 ~ 0.35m / s²; if the gradient is -6 percent, the change value of the curve's lateral acceleration is 0.2 ~ 0.45m / s², and the value range is increased.
- In the process of turning angle changing from 0 °to 7.5 °, the vehicle's lateral acceleration decreases with the upward turning angle. If the curve radius is not less than 350 m, and the curve angle is greater than 7.5 °and rises slowly, the vehicle's lateral acceleration adjustment in the curve is very minimal.
- When the vehicle has a load of 35t and is driving at a speed of 80km/h on the downhill curve road of mountain highway, the distance between the centroid of load and the front axle is less than or equal to 7000mm, and the distance between the centroid of load and the ground is less than or equal to 2300mm, which can ensure the vehicle to drive safely through the curve.

However, all kinds of road types and vehicles along Belt and Road Initiative are not analyzed separately because of the limitation of time and space. For example, the grip and load of vehicles in frozen soil and rainforest sections, and the rollover of vehicles in sharp and multi bend sections along Belt and Road Initiative. We can study all the factors and the factors that affect the safety of all roads and vehicles along the way, and make our own contribution to ensure the smoothness of the road along the Belt and Road Initiative.

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Acknowledgments

Thanks to family, friends and all support during my study. Specially (China Government Scholarship Council) for financing during my study and Professor Dr. Chen Tao for supervising me in my thesis on safety technology of Vehicle.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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